

SZ-HB-II-02-07 Connecting to cloud storage and collaborative work (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851197
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Title	Connecting to a cloud storage and collaborative work
Educational area	#higher-education
Persona	P: Vladimir - Student https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13359054 P: Kaja - student https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091286
Short description	Vladimir and Kaja must work together on a long-term, cross-university project, independent of time and location, and are looking for suitable solutions that meet the personal requirements of both of them and those of the universities.
Result	Vladimir and Kaja created documents together and transferred them into their learning management systems.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Part 1: "Data management and sharing"• Part 2: "Collaborative work"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Vladimir is registered and logged in to BIRD• Kaja is registered and logged in to BIRD
Components	#chat #workspace
Services / tools	#texteditor #PDF-annotation #open-olat #to-do-list

Problem scenario

Introduction

Vladimir Ajtraschov and Kaja Stantke are students enrolled at different universities. They are working together in a seminar within the project context "[digital state / communication design Mainz](#)" at Mainz University of Applied Sciences. Kaja is taking the course as an elective because she couldn't find anything interesting at TU Dresden and finds the subject very exciting. Vladimir is a dual student at Mainz University of Applied Sciences and is taking the seminar in his elective area. In the project context, both work with sensitive research data. The lecturers advise against using Google or Microsoft Office services.

Problem definition

Vladimir and Kaja are looking for a shared storage solution or interface. Ideally, Vladimir would still be able to transfer all files to and from his default storage location without having to save them locally first, as he also uses multiple devices. Vladimir would like the solution they plan to use for collaboration to also save jointly edited documents to Google Drive so that he can still find them in his default solution after the project is completed. He would also like to be able to upload files from Google Drive directly to the new solution.

Background and context

Kaja's values on data autonomy and sovereignty and avoids using software based on proprietary, non-open-source code, such as solutions from Google. Vladimir has a much more pragmatic approach to this topic; for him, efficiency and performance are more important than data protection issues.

The solution should also enable collaborative work. Vladimir uses Google Docs, Spreadsheets, and Presentations, but Kaja does not. Kaja uses tools that comply with data protection regulations, in this case, Cryptpad or Flinga. It is important to Kaja that the tools do not store IP addresses and location information. To ensure that both can work together and meet the university's requirements, the new solution should also enable collaborative work.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Vladimir naturally wants to work together with Kaja to be successful, so he's willing to compromise. However, he fears it will mean extra work for him, as he'll likely have to manually save the documents and import them into his standard solution after the project is completed. It's a bit annoying, because he places such high value on efficiency, and these would be tedious extra steps for him.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Vladimir and Kaja have presented their preferred tools to each other, but haven't found common ground, as Vladimir is subject to strict guidelines from his university and Kaja is very particular about the data protection compliance of the tools he uses. His previous online searches for a suitable tool have been unsuccessful.

Activity scenario

Part 1: "Data management and sharing"

Step 1: Vladimir navigates to the home page of his workspace to create a new project and names it "Research Data Seminar WS2024." The workspace serves as a central storage location for all research data and documents of the seminar team during the project.

Step 2: He selects the service he wants to link to his workspace in BIRD. To do so, they log in to Google Drive in their workspace and choose to remain logged in.

Step 3: Once the service is linked, it will show the folder structure from his Google Drive and now he can upload individual files or entire folders to the project in the workspace.

Step 4: Vladimir invites Kaja to collaborate by granting Kaja editing rights to the joint project.

Step 5: Kaja and Vladimir begin uploading relevant research data, literature and other important documents into the joint project.

Step 6: Vladimir realizes that without categorizing the data, things quickly become unstructured, so he creates subfolders to create a clear structure and starts sorting the files by data types, analysis methods or project phases.

Part 2: "Collaborative work"

Step 1: Vladimir and Kaja use OnlyOffice integrated editing tools to collaborate on documents and spreadsheets in real time.

Step 2: Using a connected PDF annotation tool, Vladimir and Kaja can mark important passages in saved PDF files and discuss them together.

Step 3: they discuss the next steps via the project chat, while they provide feedback directly in the collaboratively created documents using the comment function to minimize misunderstandings.

Step 4: Vladimir creates a to do list in his own workspace to manage the various tasks that arise during the analysis of the research data.

Step 5: Using the connected collaborative tools, tasks can be assigned by and to team members to clearly define responsibilities.

Step 6: Vladimir shares the final results with the seminar leader by making the relevant project folders available for viewing.

Step 7: Since the final submission is to be made on openOLAT, the LMS of Mainz University of Applied Sciences, Vladimir opens the LMS link on BIRD and logs in using SSO. Vladimir uploads the files to the research project course, where the instructor has already set up a submission folder.

Step 8: Since the final submission is to be made on openOLAT, the LMS of Mainz University of Applied Sciences, Vladimir opens the LMS link on BIRD, where he logs in with SSO. Vladimir uploads the files to the research project course, where the lecturer has already set up a submission folder.